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A Stage-Based Approach to Allocating Water Quality Monitoring Stations Based on the WorldQual Model: The Jubba River as a Case Study

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Abstract

Ensuring adequate freshwater quality is an important aspect of integrated environmental management and sustainable development. One contribution towards this end is to monitor the water quality of river basins. An important issue in constructing a water quality monitoring network is how to allocate the stations. This is usually done by using in situ measurements of pollutants together with other information. A stage-based optimization approach has been developed to find the optimal sites to allocate the monitoring stations. The proposed approach constructs a network in a sequence of stages without the need for in situ pollution measurements. Instead, it uses pollutant estimates from the WorldQual model together with other social and hydrological criteria. The approach is computationally efficient and provides an ordered list of stations that can be used to initialize or augment a water quality network. This is especially relevant for consideration by developing countries since, with this approach, they can get an overview of their river basins, and

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then prioritize the initial distributions of the networks. The approach was applied successfully to the 741 751 km² of the Jubba River basin, but it is applicable to river basins of any size.

Keywords: Monitoring network; Multi-objective optimization; River basin; Stage-based approach; Water quality; WorldQual model.

1 Introduction

While water covers more than two-thirds of the Earth's surface, only 2.5% of it is fresh. In developing countries, 80% of people have no access to potable water, and cholera is still present in more than 50 countries (Adu-Manu et al., 2017). Fresh water is therefore an invaluable resource which needs to be first monitored, and then properly maintained.

According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) report (UNEP, 2016), water pollution has worsened since the 1990s in many rivers in Latin America, Africa, and Asia. However, it is still possible to cut short further pollution and restore the quality of polluted rivers. In this context, there is a need to design and implement effective intervention programs to control pollution in river basins, and, when necessary, to restore them.

Water quality control is a complex issue that requires the use of support techniques to provide relevant information on water resource management. The need to monitor the water quality and budgetary constraints make it necessary to develop assessment tools that can allow efficient control of water quality. Adu-Manu et al. (2017) reviewed methods for water quality monitoring which ranged from traditional manual methods to more technologically advanced ones. More recently, Nguyen et al. (2019) presented a review of design methods for river water quality monitoring networks.

A relevant part of the design of water quality monitoring networks is to establish the location of the stations. A well-designed network is one that provides the greatest possible amount of information from the fewest number of stations, so that the overall cost of monitoring is less. Several authors have addressed this issue from different viewpoints and based on different information.

Park et al. (2006) considered a genetic algorithm in a geographic information system framework to allocate monitoring stations in river basins. An optimization problem was formulated by considering different planning objectives such as compliance with water quality standards through biochemical

31 oxygen demand measurements in the dry season, observation of water use,
32 tracking of sources of pollution, and examination of water quality changes.
33 A different approach, also based on a genetic algorithm, allowed Telci et al.
34 (2009) to address this allocation problem based on the minimization of the
35 average detection time of contamination events and the maximization of the
36 reliability of the monitoring system at the same time as keeping the num-
37 ber of stations to a minimum. Remote sensing images were used by Chang
38 & Makkeasorn (2010) who proposed an approach based on “grey integer
39 programming” to select the locations considering a number of biophysical
40 parameters and a budgetary constraint. Liyanage et al. (2016) considered a
41 genetic algorithm to optimize avoidance of water quality standards violations,
42 the population affected, distance of the site from the nearest downstream wa-
43 ter intake, and coverage of upstream area. A fitness function was defined as
44 the weighted sum (with weights defined by experts) of the partial objective
45 functions with the number of stations included. Puri et al. (2017) proposed
46 a genetic algorithm to select monitoring stations using mean annual *E. coli*
47 flux data from the Spatially Referenced Regression Model on Watershed At-
48 tributes. The objectives were to minimize the number of monitoring stations,
49 to cover large mean annual *E. coli* fluxes, and to minimize the uncertainty
50 in the flux estimates. Constraints related to monitoring critical locations
51 were also included in a multi-objective optimization problem. Zhu et al.
52 (2019) implemented a discrete particle swarm optimization procedure for the
53 allocation of water quality monitoring stations based on minimum pollution
54 detection time, maximum pollution detection probability, and maximum cen-
55 trality of monitoring locations while allowing reservation of some particular
56 locations. This was done by considering the reduction of redundant moni-
57 toring locations.

58 The water quality parameters most commonly monitored correspond to
59 general physicochemical characteristics (Nguyen et al., 2019). Villas-Boas
60 et al. (2017) considered thirteen water quality parameters based on in situ
61 measurements that were analysed in the laboratory. They identified the
62 most relevant parameters, and showed how some of them were redundant
63 and could be removed without significant information loss. However, obtain-
64 ing many in situ measurements is both very costly and difficult to implement
65 in many river basins, so some approaches have been developed based on pol-
66 lutant simulations given by hydrological models. Al-Khafaji & Abdulraheem
67 (2017) proposed a deterministic algorithm for the determination of optimal
68 water quality monitoring stations based on two-dimensional hydrodynamic

69 and water quality simulation models that had been used to estimate the dis-
70 tribution of total dissolved solids. Pérez et al. (2017) considered estimates
71 of pollutant parameters such as biochemical oxygen demand, faecal coliform
72 bacteria, and total dissolved solids from the WorldQual model (Voß et al.,
73 2012) to feed a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm implemented in the
74 framework of a geographic information system.

75 Assessing global water quality issues requires a multi-pollutant modelling
76 approach. Stokral et al. (2019) focused on the need to integrate informa-
77 tion on sources of pollutants such as plastic debris, nutrients, chemicals,
78 and pathogens, among others. Vital signs for water quality usually cover
79 some water quality parameters such as dissolved oxygen, temperature, salin-
80 ity (total dissolved solids or electric conductivity), pH, turbidity, and faecal
81 coliforms, among others. Impairments of these can produce an impact to
82 the flora and/or fauna for a given water body. McCaffrey (2012) described
83 some water quality parameters and provided their acceptable ranges. They
84 also focused on their effects, for example, the temperature of the water is
85 relevant because the amount of oxygen that will dissolve in water increases
86 as the temperature decreases. Stokral et al. (2019) illustrated the potential
87 of multi-pollutant modelling for hotspot analyses, and discussed scientific
88 challenges and future directions for multi-pollutant modelling.

89 Sparse-data scenarios are especially interesting, and some approaches
90 have been developed for such situations. Bastidas et al. (2017) designed
91 water quality monitoring networks via optimization techniques, geographic
92 information system technology, and a “matter-element” analysis of 5-day
93 biological oxygen demand and total suspended solids. Scenarios with and
94 without historical water quality data were addressed. Alilou et al. (2019)
95 proposed a multi-criteria evaluation method including the analytic network
96 process and fuzzy logic to identify locations of sampling points based on a
97 “total potential pollution score” calculated without water quality data as in-
98 put. This approach prioritizes the best candidate sampling points, and can
99 be applied in settings where water quality data are scarce.

100 Redesigning water quality monitoring networks has also been addressed
101 in the scientific literature. Sabzipour et al. (2019) applied two geostatistical
102 methods, ordinary kriging and sequential Gaussian simulation, to electrical
103 conductivity and dissolved oxygen concentration data, showing that the sta-
104 tions involved could be relocated to achieve an optimized network. Bastidas
105 et al. (2017) also proposed a methodological approach which they used to
106 redesign water quality networks.

107 In the present paper, a stage-based approach to allocating water qual-
108 ity monitoring stations is described and applied. This approach is based on
109 the WorldQual model, a continental-scale water quality model that has been
110 developed to obtain simulations of some pollutant loadings and in-stream
111 concentrations in river basins. With the WorldQual model, such pollutants
112 as biochemical oxygen demand, faecal coliform bacteria, and total dissolved
113 solids can be estimated for any river worldwide. Besides detecting areas
114 with pollutants, other planning objectives can be optimized, such as popula-
115 tion, hydrological categorization, and the number of stations. The algorithm
116 was developed to allow progressive selection of the stations, and is based on
117 multi-objective artificial bee colony (MOABC) optimization. It is able to
118 find optimal solutions from a very large number of alternatives in a com-
119 putationally efficient way. It can be used to establish an initial network for
120 river basins with no pre-existing network or in situ measurements, and then
121 also to subsequently increase the number of stations in the network. The
122 proposed approach was applied to the Jubba River basin (eastern Africa)
123 whose drainage area is 741 751 km².

124 The main advantages of this proposal are:

- 125 • It uses pollutant estimates from the WorldQual model to detect non-
126 compliance areas.
- 127 • Its approach is one of stage-based multi-objective optimization (MOABC).
- 128 • It is able to efficiently reduce the number of possible solutions to allow
129 just one optimal solution to be chosen.
- 130 • It can be used both to establish a new network and then to progressively
131 augment it.
- 132 • It is valid for river basins worldwide of any size.

133 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the
134 motivation for the proposed approach. Section 3 describes the study area,
135 the WorldQual model, the planning objectives, and the optimization method.
136 Section 4 presents and discusses the experimental results, and finally, Section
137 5 presents the conclusions.

138 2. The Motivating Problem

139 The decision of where to allocate the monitoring stations is an important
140 part of the process of designing a water quality network. Many river basins
141 around the world have no water quality monitoring networks, and the water
142 quality data available in many parts of the world is inadequate.

143 The Global Environment Monitoring System for freshwater (GEMS/ Wa-
144 ter) programme¹ was established more than 40 years ago to collect global
145 water quality data to assess the status and trends of global inland water
146 quality. Under the auspices of the UNEP, the GEMS/Water programme
147 involves the World Health Organization (WHO), the World Meteorologi-
148 cal Organization (WMO), and the United Nations Educational, Scientific
149 and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). This programme uses GEMStat as a
150 database of surface and ground water quality data. According to this GEM-
151 Stat database, 71 of the 110 river basins with data have a density of at most
152 0.5 stations/10 000 km². The average densities for Latin America, Asia, and
153 Africa are, respectively, 0.3, 0.08, and 0.02 stations/10 000 km² for the time
154 period 1990 to 2010. Therefore, the GEMStat database station density is far
155 below the typical minimum densities of around 1.5 to 4 stations/10 000 km²
156 of the river basins of Europe and the USA (UNEP, 2016).

157 There is no internationally accepted scientific standardized process for
158 the design of water monitoring networks. WMO (1994) provided a recom-
159 mended minimum network density for different physiographic units (coastal,
160 mountains, interior plains, hilly, small islands, and polar/arid). Borden &
161 Roy (2015), through the International Institute for Sustainable Development
162 (IISD), summarized the WMO recommendations for the minimum number of
163 stations in three physiographic units: flat (1 station/1000-2000 km²), moun-
164 tainous (1 station/300-1000 km²), and arid (1 station/5000-20 000 km²).
165 However, it was made clear that the recommendations are general and the
166 final network density should be based on particular criteria such as network
167 objectives or availability of finance and other resources.

168 To analyse the impact of the size of rivers on how best to locate the
169 stations, it would be useful to have a categorization of their basins in terms
170 of size. Again, there is no consensus on a standard categorization in this
171 sense. Nguyen et al. (2019) presented a categorization by river basin area
172 with the following classes: small (<100 km²), medium (100-1000 km²), large

¹<http://www.unep.org/gemswater/>

173 (1000-10 000 km²), and very large (>10 000 km²), with reference to Higgins
 174 et al. (2005), Noble & Cowx (2002), and European Parliament and Council
 175 (2000). Those authors (Nguyen et al., 2019) reported that most studies in
 176 the literature concerned very large rivers in high- to middle-income countries.

177 In Africa, Asia, and South America there are, respectively, 8104, 45 804,
 178 and 9926 river basins, with mean areas in km² (\pm standard deviation) of
 179 3712 \pm 64 044, 1025 \pm 28 178, and 1815 \pm 66 295, respectively. Figure
 180 1 displays the comparative box plots for the area distributions of the river
 181 basins. All three distributions are strongly positively skewed, with many
 182 small river basins and few large ones.

Figure 1: Box plots for the size distribution of the river basin areas in Africa, Asia, and South America.

183 According to UNEP (2016), in Africa, the average density of stations per
 184 10 000 km² is 0.02. The Jubba River basin comprises parts of Somalia, Kenya,
 185 and Ethiopia, covering an area of 741 751 km². This value corresponds to
 186 the 99th percentile, which means that it is one of the largest rivers in Africa.
 187 The water of the Jubba River basin is very important for food production in
 188 this area. Water resources are strongly influenced by seasonal floods. A hy-
 189 drometric network was operating in southern Somalia before the civil war in
 190 1991, when data collection was abandoned until 2001 with the rebuilding of

191 a much reduced network (Houghton-Carr et al., 2011). The objective of this
192 rebuilt network was to measure rainfall, river flow, groundwater resources,
193 land characteristics, degradation, and land suitability as well as to improve
194 flood warning and flood management. To the best of the authors' knowledge,
195 the network's stations do not provide accessible regular water quality infor-
196 mation. Indeed, the GEMStat database does not report any water quality
197 monitoring network in the Jubba River basin.

198 As an example, this situation motivates the need to develop tools that
199 can help the authorities allocate water quality monitoring stations based on
200 objective criteria that can be easily obtained without requiring actual in situ
201 pollutant measurements. Using low-cost criteria such as pollutant estimates
202 given by the WorldQual model to detect non-compliance areas may help
203 in this task, and are applicable to river basins of any size anywhere in the
204 world. If this is done in a progressive way, the approach could be useful
205 both for constructing a new water quality network and for augmenting an
206 existing network. While this is especially relevant for rivers where no water
207 quality networks have been established, it can also be applied to progressively
208 reconstruct old ones. Such progressive increase of a network also facilitates
209 accommodation to different budgets.

210 **3. Methods**

211 *3.1. Study area*

212 The Jubba River is an important east African river located in southern
213 Somalia. Its source is at the border with Ethiopia, and it flows directly south
214 to empty into the Indian Ocean at Goobweyn. The two main tributaries, the
215 Shebelle and Lagh Dera rivers, join the Jubba River close to its mouth. Balint
216 et al. (2010) defined three catchment areas for this zone (Jubba, Shebelle, and
217 Lagh Dera), although only the Jubba River has access to the sea. Together,
218 these three catchments constitute the present work's study area, which we
219 shall term the Jubba River basin. This basin drains a total of 741 751 km²
220 and extends across parts of Somalia, Kenya, and Ethiopia (see Figure 2 for
221 the location and distribution of the tributaries).

222 *3.2. WorldQual model*

223 The WorldQual model is a global scale water quality model (Voß et al.,
224 2012). It is a module of WaterGAP3 (Water Global Assessment and Progno-

Figure 2: The Jubba-Shebelle-Lagh basin and its location in eastern Africa.

225 sis), which is a global water assessment model consisting of a global water use
 226 model and a global hydrology model (Alcamo et al., 2003; Verzano, 2009).

227 Voß et al. (2012) presented WorldQual, and illustrated its performance
 228 in applying it to model biological oxygen demand (BOD) and total dissolved
 229 solids (TDS) across Europe. The model was extended to model faecal coliform
 230 (FC) loadings for large European rivers and the resulting in-stream
 231 concentrations (Reder et al., 2015). It has also been applied to model FC and
 232 BOD in African rivers (Reder et al., 2014). Indeed, it is the only large-scale
 233 concentration model which has been applied to faecal coliform bacteria for
 234 various continents (Vermeulen et al., 2019). It has been validated and tested
 235 with a global sensitivity and uncertainty analysis (Reder et al., 2017).

236 The WorldQual model operates on monthly time steps and a 5-by-5 arc-
 237 minute grid spatial resolution (approximately 9-by-9 km at the equator).
 238 This resolution divides the Jubba River basin into 8710 cells of about 85
 239 km² each in accordance with the drainage direction map of Lehner et al.
 240 (2008). Estimated concentrations of BOD, FC, and TDS were obtained from
 241 January 1990 to December 2010 on a monthly basis.

242 Figure 3 represents the entire Jubba River basin divided into main and
 243 secondary stretches based on Strahler stream order (Strahler, 1957). The

244 streams of the river basin are represented as a mathematical tree, and the
 245 Strahler number is a numerical measure of their branching complexity. A
 246 stream with no children is a leaf, and its Strahler number is one. Such
 247 streams are regarded as secondary, and the remaining ones as main. Main
 248 channels (streams with Strahler number greater than one) are candidates for
 249 the allocation of stations.

Figure 3: Grid representation of the Jubba River basin with main and secondary channels.

250 3.3. Planning objectives

251 In order to find macro-locations at which to optimally allocate water
 252 quality monitoring stations, planning objectives based on economic, environ-
 253 mental, social, and hydrological aspects are defined. Examples of the use
 254 of such planning objectives are found in Park et al. (2006), Liyanage et al.
 255 (2016), and Pérez et al. (2017).

256 Let X_{ij} denote a binary variable for the cell (i, j) in the river basin grid,
 257 with i being the index representing the row and j the index representing the

258 column. This variable determines whether the cell (i, j) is ($X_{ij} = 1$) or is not
 259 ($X_{ij} = 0$) assigned to allocate a station. For the Jubba River basin, there
 260 are a total of 3097 candidate stations, which are labeled as main channels
 261 in Figure 3. The vector of binary components denoted by \mathbf{x} represents the
 262 solution of the allocation problem.

263 A first criterion is to reduce the economic cost of building the water
 264 quality monitoring network. This is achieved by keeping the number of mon-
 265 itoring stations to a minimum. Mathematically, this is defined as minimizing
 266 the following objective function:

$$\phi_1(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i,j} X_{ij}. \quad (1)$$

267 Detecting lower compliance areas is the second criterion considered, which
 268 is related to an environmental aspect. This criterion is established so that
 269 the network shows the greatest potential capability to detect polluted ar-
 270 eas. Mathematically, this is translated into maximizing the probabilities of
 271 detecting threshold violations. With the WorldQual model, the in-stream
 272 concentrations of BOD, FC, and TDS were estimated for each grid cell of
 273 the Jubba River basin on a monthly basis for a period of 21 years. These
 274 quantities are denoted for BOD, FC, and TDS, respectively, by $U_{ij}^{(t)}$, $V_{ij}^{(t)}$,
 275 and $W_{ij}^{(t)}$, for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, where $T = 252 = 12 \cdot 21$ is the total number
 276 of simulated measurements over the entire period for each pollutant. Values
 277 of BOD, FC, and TDS under 4 mg/l, 200 cfu/100 ml (colony-forming units
 278 per 100 ml), and 450 mg/l, respectively, are acceptable (UNEP, 2016). The
 279 probabilities of detection of threshold violations of BOD (U_{ij}), FC (V_{ij}), and
 280 TDS (W_{ij}) for each grid cell over the whole period of time are defined as:

$$P(U_{ij} > 4) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T I[U_{ij}^{(t)} > 4], \quad (2)$$

$$P(V_{ij} > 200) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T I[V_{ij}^{(t)} > 200], \quad (3)$$

$$P(W_{ij} > 450) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T I[W_{ij}^{(t)} > 450], \quad (4)$$

281 where $I[\cdot]$ represents the indicator function.

282 The above probabilities are combined into a single value representing each
 283 cell, denoted Water Pollution Detection (WPD). This measure is defined for

284 each cell as $D_{ij} = P(U_{ij} > 4) + P(V_{ij} > 200) + P(W_{ij} > 450)$. The greater
 285 the value of D_{ij} , the more pollution that cell contains. Therefore, cells with
 286 large values should be preferred for allocating stations in order to detect
 287 non-compliance areas. Figure 4 shows the WPD values in the Jubba River
 288 basin.

Figure 4: WPD for the cells in the Jubba River basin.

289 The objective function is defined as:

$$\phi_2(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i,j} D_{ij} \cdot X_{ij}, \quad (5)$$

290 which should be maximized.

291 The third criterion considers the population involved. The degree of pro-
 292 tection of areas with large populations takes into account a social dimension.
 293 The areas with greater populations should be preferred for allocating moni-
 294 toring stations over those with fewer people. This information is available in
 295 the WorldQual model, and the population count in each cell is denoted by
 296 C_{ij} . Figure 5 represents the population in each cell of the Jubba River basin.

Figure 5: Population for the cells in the Jubba River basin.

297 Therefore, the objective function to maximize is:

$$\phi_3(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i,j} C_{ij} \cdot X_{ij}. \quad (6)$$

298 The last criterion is related to a hydrological aspect, involving a classifica-
 299 tion of the river basin stretches. The Strahler (or Horton–Strahler) number
 300 of the mathematical tree representing the river basin will be considered for
 301 this task (Horton, 1945; Strahler, 1957). The Strahler number for a node in
 302 that tree is just its number of children. It is a numerical measure of branch-
 303 ing complexity, and is used to define stream size based on a hierarchy of
 304 tributaries. Let S_{ij} denote the variable representing the Strahler number of
 305 the cell (i, j) . The greater the Strahler number, the more importance the
 306 cell has hydrologically. These numbers may be of great help to avoid the
 307 concentration of stations in areas of low hydrological importance. Figure 6
 308 represents the Strahler number for the cells in the Jubba River basin.

Figure 6: Strahler number for the cells in the Jubba River basin.

309 The objective function to maximize is:

$$\phi_4(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i,j} S_{ij} \cdot X_{ij}. \quad (7)$$

310 Besides the objective functions, two constraints are considered. The first
 311 is related to the maximum budget allowed. The total number of stations
 312 should be between a minimum m ($m \geq 1$) and a maximum M . The second is
 313 related to neighbouring cells. This constraint is aimed at avoiding touching
 314 cells from being selected.

315 Finally, the problem of how to allocate monitoring stations is defined as a
 316 multi-objective optimization problem in which the number of stations is min-
 317 imized (Equation (1)) over a certain range of values while avoiding touching
 318 cells at the same time as maximizing the detection of non-compliance areas
 319 (Equation (5)), the population in the area (Equation (6)), and the hydrolog-
 320 ical importance (Equation (7)).

321 *3.4. Stage-based multi-objective optimization algorithm*

322 The optimization problem defined in the previous subsection contains
323 multiple conflicting objectives. Multi-objective optimization is the natural
324 way to solve it.

325 The Multi-Objective Artificial Bee Colony (MOABC) algorithm is an ex-
326 tension to multi-objective settings of the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algo-
327 rithm proposed by Karaboga & Basturk (2007). MOABC is an evolutionary
328 algorithm based on the intelligent foraging behaviour of honey bee swarms
329 with a population defined as a colony with three groups of bees: (1) employed
330 bees maintain the currently known solutions of the problem; (2) onlooker bees
331 allow the exploitation of the best solutions found so far; and (3) scout bees
332 allow the exploration of new solutions when some of the current solutions are
333 exhausted (they cannot be further improved). This algorithm allows escape
334 from local optima, and provides good approximations to the overall opti-
335 mum. MOABC has been successfully applied in several contexts (see, e.g.,
336 Karaboga et al. (2014); Pérez et al. (2017); Huo & Liu (2018)).

337 In the present work, the MOABC algorithm was adapted to find optimal
338 solutions in different stages by means of an efficient implementation that al-
339 lows the allocation problem to be solved for river basins of any size. In spite
340 of the fact that multi-objective optimization returns a set of non-dominated
341 solutions, the proposed approach considers at each stage consensus stations
342 which properly approach the overall optima. Algorithm 1 presents the pseu-
343 docode for the stage-based MOABC approach. A detailed explanation of
344 the MOABC algorithm (lines 3-15) can be found in Pérez et al. (2017). In
345 the present work, a stage-based version of MOABC is proposed. In this new
346 version, the process is repeated for a maximum number of stages (line 2).
347 Here, three stages will be considered. Each stage increases the number of
348 stations used, taking into account the stations fixed in the previous stage.
349 The first stage has no station fixed (line 1). Once MOABC has obtained the
350 non-dominated solutions for that stage, they are saved (line 16) and are used
351 to generate the consensus stations (line 17), i.e., the stations most used by
352 all the non-dominated solutions. These consensus stations are saved as the
353 exact solution for that stage (line 18). The consensus stations will then be
354 used as fixed stations (line 19), adding more stations during the processing
355 of the next stage.

356 The stage-based MOABC algorithm was configured with parameters that
357 had been tested to work appropriately, i.e., a colony size of 50, a maximum

Algorithm 1 Stage-based MOABC pseudocode.

```
1: fixed_stations  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: for stage = 1 to max_stages do
3:   non_dominated_solutions  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
4:   #Problem-aware and random generation of the initial colony
5:   initial(fixed_stations)
6:   #Main steps of MOABC are repeated max. cycles or generations
7:   for cycle = 1 to max_cycles do
8:     send_employed_bees(fixed_stations)
9:     rank_and_crowding(colony_size)
10:    calculate_probabilities()
11:    send_onlooker_bees(fixed_stations)
12:    send_scout_bees(fixed_stations, cycle)
13:    rank_and_crowding(2 * colony_size)
14:    non_dominated_solutions  $\leftarrow$  export_colony()
15:  end for
16:  save_non_dominated_solutions(non_dominated_solutions, stage)
17:  consensus_stations  $\leftarrow$  get_consensus(non_dominated_solutions)
18:  save_consensus_stations(consensus_stations, stage)
19:  fixed_stations  $\leftarrow$  fixed_stations  $\cup$  consensus_stations
20: end for
```

358 number of cycles of 3000, and a number of tries of 100 before taking a solu-
359 tion to be exhausted. Similar parameter values were proposed by the ABC
360 authors². Other values were tested for each of these parameters, but the best
361 results were obtained with this configuration.

362 In order to ensure the statistical reliability of the results, the execution
363 of the algorithm was repeated 31 times because of the stochastic nature of
364 the proposed algorithm. The median results obtained from these 31 inde-
365 pendent runs will be presented in the Results and Discussion section. This
366 is a usual procedure in the optimization field since it avoids only the best
367 execution being chosen and provides fairer information about the algorithm's
368 performance (Birattari & Dorigo, 2007).

369 Finally, scatter plots will be used to represent the non-dominated solu-

²<http://mf.erciyes.edu.tr/abc/>

370 tions for each stage, and graphs and descriptive statistics to compare the
371 objective values by stages.

372 4. Results and Discussion

373 This section will present a detailed analysis of the solutions obtained in
374 each stage. Then a comparative analysis of the results of the stages will be
375 made, followed by a discussion of the stage-based selection of water monitor-
376 ing stations.

377 4.1. Defining the stages

378 The Jubba River basin has a drainage area of 741 751 km^2 in a region
379 with an arid climate. According to the minimum number of stations defined
380 by WMO (WMO, 1994) and summarized by Borden & Roy (2015) of the
381 IISD, arid regions should have at least 1 station/5000-20 000 km^2 . This
382 would mean between 37 and 148 water quality monitoring stations in the
383 network. But, according to the GEMStat database, the average density for
384 African river basins is 0.02 stations/10 000 km^2 , which is very low compared
385 to typical minimum densities of around 1.5 to 4 stations/10 000 km^2 of
386 river basins in Europe and the USA (UNEP, 2016). These latter values for
387 Europe and the USA would mean that there should be from 112 to 296
388 stations allocated to the Jubba River basin. Combining the two criteria,
389 it would seem reasonable to establish a network with 112 stations for this
390 large drainage area. Moreover, to be affordable, this should be performed in
391 stages. A three-stage approach is proposed here, with the first comprising
392 20 stations, the second incorporating additional 30 stations, and the third
393 adding the remaining 62 stations to the 50 stations already allocated in the
394 two previous stages.

395 4.2. First stage: from 1 to 20 monitoring stations

396 In the execution of this stage-based MOABC algorithm, a set of non-
397 dominated solutions is generated. In the first stage, each solution corresponds
398 to from 1 to 20 locations where the monitoring stations can be placed. Specif-
399 ically, 880 different non-dominated solutions are obtained in the first stage
400 for the median execution. Note that the four objectives are being optimized
401 simultaneously, so that the graphical representation of the solutions involves
402 four dimensions. For better understanding, the graphical representation will

403 be decomposed into six 2D plots that include all the possible pairwise combi-
404 nations of the four objectives. The objective values of these non-dominated
405 solutions are shown in Figure 7.

(a) WPD vs number of stations.

(b) Strahler number vs number of stations.

(c) Population vs number of stations.

(d) WPD vs population.

(e) WPD vs Strahler number.

(f) Population vs Strahler number.

Figure 7: Objective values of the non-dominated solutions obtained when the number of monitoring stations is limited to between 1 and 20.

The following deductions can be made from the plots in Figure 7. Figure

407 7(a) shows that non-dominated solutions are obtained for all numbers of sta-
408 tions between 1 and 20, and that the dispersion increases with the number
409 of stations. The more stations there are, the greater is WPD. This was to
410 be expected since the greater the number of stations, the more threshold vi-
411 olations will be detectable. The relationship between the number of stations
412 and the Strahler number is shown in Figure 7(b). Again as expected, when
413 the number of stations increases, the Strahler number also increases since it
414 is possible to cover more river stretches with high hydrological importance.
415 The increase in the dispersion stands out more in Figure 7(c) with more
416 population being covered as more stations are considered. This would result
417 in more people being protected. Figure 7(d) shows that when the popula-
418 tion increases, the WPD also increases. Areas with high population may
419 produce more pollution in general, and hence greater water contamination.
420 Figure 7(e) shows two types of behaviour for the relationship between the
421 Strahler number and WPD. First, for most of the solutions, as the Strahler
422 number increases, so does the WPD with a steep slope. This means that
423 these solutions represent stations at which the pollution increases strongly
424 with their growing hydrological importance. Second, there is another group
425 of solutions for which this increase is weaker. Finally, Figure 7(f) shows that,
426 as the Strahler number increases, so does the population. This means that
427 people settle in areas close to important streams.

428 This procedure allowed the $2.56 \cdot 10^{51}$ possible solutions for from 1 to
429 20 monitoring stations to be reduced to the best 880 solutions (i.e., greater
430 than 99.99% reduction). Now the best 20 locations based on these 880 non-
431 dominated solutions have to be selected. To this end, a procedure based on
432 the consensus solution is applied. The frequency of each cell (i.e., the number
433 of times that the cell is present in these 880 non-dominated solutions) is
434 calculated, and all the cells are ranked according to those frequencies. The
435 20 most repeated cells are then taken to be the locations of the monitoring
436 stations given by this first stage.

437 *4.3. Second stage: from 21 to 50 monitoring stations*

438 Now the focus turns to the next 30 monitoring stations, given that the
439 first 20 have been settled. In this case, a total of 2352 different non-dominated
440 solutions were found in the median execution. The objective values of these
441 non-dominated solutions are shown in Figure 8.

(a) WPD vs number of stations.

(b) Strahler number vs number of stations.

(c) Population vs number of stations.

(d) WPD vs population.

(e) WPD vs Strahler number.

(f) Population vs Strahler number.

Figure 8: All the non-dominated solutions obtained when the number of monitoring stations is limited to between 21 and 50.

443 but with some additional remarks. The increase in the number of solutions
444 leads to greater dispersion than in the first stage. This can be seen in the
445 relationship between the number of stations and each of the three objectives
446 (Figures 8 (a,b,c)). While again WPD increases as the population grows,
447 there now appear three positive slopes which correspond to three different
448 areas related to the Strahler numbers (see Figures 8 (d, e)). In Figure 8 (f),
449 one observes that larger Strahler numbers are related to lower populations.

450 Since the process is progressive, in this stage there are 3077 (=3097-20)
451 possible locations. The number of possible solutions with between 21 and 50
452 stations is then $5.71 \cdot 10^{109}$, which the algorithm reduces to 2352 solutions
453 (again greater than 99.99% reduction). The consensus solution approach was
454 applied to get the 30 best new locations for this second stage.

455 *4.4. Third stage: from 51 to 112 monitoring stations*

456 Now the focus is on allocating the last 62 monitoring stations given that
457 the first 50 have been settled in the previous stages. A total of 6283 non-
458 dominated solutions were found in the median execution. The objective
459 values of these non-dominated solutions are shown in Figure 9.

(a) WPD vs number of stations.

(b) Strahler number vs number of stations.

(c) Population vs number of stations.

(d) WPD vs population.

(e) WPD vs Strahler number.

(f) Population vs Strahler number.

Figure 9: All the non-dominated solutions obtained when the number of monitoring stations is limited to between 51 and 112.

460

The same trends for the objectives observed in the second stage are even

461 clearer now due to the greater number of solutions found.

462 In this stage, there are 3047 (3097-50) possible locations for the stations
463 51 to 112. In this stage, there are $1.04 \cdot 10^{207}$ possible solutions, which the
464 algorithm reduces to 6283, a computationally manageable number. Appli-
465 cation of the consensus solution approach allowed the best 62 new locations
466 to be determined for this stage. Combination with the solutions found in
467 the previous stages yielded an ordered list of 112 locations for water quality
468 monitoring stations.

469 4.5. Description of the monitoring station locations

470 Figure 10 shows the locations of the water quality monitoring stations by
471 stage.

Figure 10: Progressive allocation of 112 monitoring stations in three stages.

472 The first stage assigned stations in different important areas. Specifically,
473 stretches with low Strahler number and high pollution were assigned as sta-

474 tions in the north and northwest of the Jubba River basin (in Ethiopia). In
475 the centre of the river basin (in Somalia), the stations assigned corresponded
476 to sites with very high Strahler number and population but low pollution.
477 Some stations were allocated in the east of the river basin, mainly corre-
478 sponding to the Shebelle tributary. These stretches have very high Strahler
479 numbers and high pollution. Finally, some stations were allocated close to
480 the mouth, along the Jubba River itself. They combine high population with
481 the maximum Strahler numbers, but not high pollution.

482 The second stage reinforces the coverage of some of the vast areas de-
483 scribed for the previous stage, and adds stations in the southwest of the
484 Jubba River basin (Kenya) with intermediate pollution, high population,
485 and low Strahler numbers.

486 Finally, the third stage increases the coverage of all of the previously
487 defined areas, and adds focuses on three new areas. One is in the west of
488 the river basin (Ethiopia) with locations having low Strahler numbers and
489 intermediate population and pollution. Another is around the Kutulo and
490 Lak Bor tributaries (Kenya and Somalia) where the locations assigned have
491 low population and Strahler number, but high pollution. The last area with
492 assigned stations corresponds to the Lagh Dera tributary, especially close to
493 where it flows into the Jubba River. These locations have low pollution and
494 population, but very high Strahler number.

495 The construction of this network based on objective criteria has thus been
496 able to allocate in a progressive way the water quality monitoring stations
497 in the most significant parts of the river basin. The following subsection will
498 compare the performance of the objective values in the three stages.

499 *4.6. The performance of the stage-based approach*

500 As was described above, the procedure was defined so that the number
501 of stations increases up to 112 in three stages. This subsection will present a
502 comparison of the evolution of the objective values for the locations selected
503 in the three stages. Since the stations were ranked within each stage, it is
504 possible to conform a water quality network with any number of stations
505 from 1 to 112. Figure 11 presents the cumulative WPD for any number of
506 stations together with its disaggregation by FC, BOD, and TDS.

Figure 11: Cumulative amounts of WPD, FC, BOD, and TDS for from 1 to 112 stations.

507 Figure 11 shows a major increase of cumulative WPD during the first
 508 stage, with a more moderate rise during the other stages. Specifically, the
 509 slopes are 1.23, 0.70, and 0.85 for the first, second, and third stages, respec-
 510 tively. This behaviour shows that the first stations are very well allocated,
 511 covering the locations with the highest WPD. Then, as the number of mon-
 512 itoring stations increases, it becomes harder to proportionally detect this
 513 pollution because the best locations have already been assigned. The infor-
 514 mation in this figure would allow an exact number of stations for the network
 515 to be found for any threshold established for cumulative WPD. The disag-
 516 gregated information shows that FC contributes the most, followed by BOD,
 517 and finally by TDS, and that this is the case for whatever number of stations.
 518 Again, a threshold of cumulative FC, BOD, or TDS could be established in
 519 order to find the exact number of stations required for the network.

520 Figure 12 is the analogous graph for the population. The slope of the
 521 cumulative population curve is steep to begin with, and then gradually starts

522 to flatten out as the number of stations increases. In particular, the slope
523 decreases from 49 267 in the first stage to 12 748 in the second and 5098 in
524 the third. Again, this indicates that the first stations are very well allocated,
525 and then the next stations become harder to match such a high benefit.
526 This caveat notwithstanding, the graph allows a population threshold to be
527 established so as to find the exact number of stations that need to be set up
528 in the network.

Figure 12: Cumulative population for from 1 to 112 stations.

529 Finally, the corresponding graph for the Strahler numbers is shown in
530 Figure 13. In this case, the cumulative Strahler number curve has a fairly
531 constant upward slope across all three stages, reflecting that a steadily grow-
532 ing number of streams are being monitored by the network. Again, the graph
533 would allow a Strahler number threshold to be established to find the exact
534 number of stations needed in the network.

Figure 13: Cumulative Strahler numbers for from 1 to 112 stations.

535 By way of synthesis, Table 1 lists the objective values (WPD, population,
 536 and Strahler number) for each stage, as well as the percentage improvement
 537 of each stage over the preceding one.

Stage	WPD	Population	Strahler
1	25.08 -	1 013 221 -	88 -
2	47.10 87.80%	1 417 275 39.88%	205 132.95%
3	99.72 111.72%	1 740 415 22.80%	414 101.95%

Table 1: Objective values and percentage improvements for WPD, population, and Strahler number by stages.

538 For WPD, the percentage improvement from the first to the second stage
 539 is 87.80%, increasing to 111.72% from the second to the third stage. For the
 540 population objective, the respective improvements are 39.88% and 22.80%,
 541 and for the Strahler numbers they are both greater than 100%. Observe
 542 that percentage improvements higher than 100% are possible because the
 543 increment of monitoring stations from stage 1 to stage 2 is 150% (from 20 to
 544 50 stations) and the augmentation of stations from stage 2 to stage 3 is 124%
 545 (from 50 to 112 stations). It can be concluded that the data from Table 1
 546 lend support to the applicability of the proposed stage-based approach to
 547 substantially improving the objectives being considered with increases in the
 548 number of stations.

549 5. Conclusions

550 A stage-based optimization approach has been developed to construct
 551 river basin water quality monitoring networks. The approach allows a net-
 552 work to be created from scratch without the need for in situ pollution mea-
 553 surements. Instead, it uses, together with other social and hydrological cri-
 554 teria, pollutant estimates from the WorldQual model. At each stage, the
 555 proposed stage-based MOABC approach is able to efficiently reduce the huge
 556 number of possible solutions, and choose just one optimal solution. Moreover,
 557 the method followed provides a list of candidate stations ranked by impor-
 558 tance, so that the network can be built up progressively. This approach is
 559 especially interesting when in situ measurements are absent since it allows a

560 water quality network to be initialized and augmented. It can be applied to
561 river basins of any size.

562 The results show that the approach finds the best places to allocate mon-
563 itoring stations in the Jubba River basin by seeking a compromise between
564 detection of pollutants, number of people affected, and the location's hydro-
565 logical importance. At the same time, the number of stations required is
566 reduced as much as possible – an aspect that is especially relevant for ap-
567 plication by developing countries who may consider this approach as a way
568 to obtain an overview of their river basins and then prioritize the initial dis-
569 tributions of the networks. The approach would help policy makers to take
570 informed decisions based on environmental and sustainability assessments of
571 their river basins.

572 As a future research line, this approach could be adapted to include more
573 pollutants and water information, such as microplastics, nutrients, chemicals,
574 pathogens, temperature, among others, with a previous correlation study
575 that clarifies the possible relationships among all this information.

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